

Effect of photoactive carbon nitride and titanium dioxide features on HKUST-1 depositions and catalytic consequences during CO₂ conversion in water

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ABSTRACT

“CO₂ storage is one of the biggest challenges in controlling climate change. It can either be stored permanently or recycled into chemicals for which photoreduction of CO₂ is a promising method by providing a way to enable conversion into high value chemicals with sunlight. Photoactive supports, such as carbon nitride or titanium dioxide catalyze this conversion and mesoporous materials can enhance substrate uptake by increasing surface area and adsorption. Metal-organic frameworks (MOF) deposition on such materials enables to increase substrate specificity and direct conversion into desired products. Since MOFs are affected by environmental factors, such as pH, temperature or co-ligands during their formation and interaction, structural differences in photoactive support will impact behavior and affect productivity of acetaldehyde and ethanol from CO₂ and water within HKUST-1@support heterojunctions. This investigation compares morphological and photocatalytic effects of growing HKUST-1 on graphitic carbon nitride, mesoporous carbon nitride and TiO₂. By adding MOF layers in a stepwise process, we investigate surface binding and interaction on each support in photoreduction of CO₂ in a closed batch system under room temperature. Such methods allow us to study the effect of support-interactions on MOF growth and cross-reference to the observed photocatalytic activity. This leads to a shift towards ethanol productivity with selectivity of up to 63 % compared to acetaldehyde in the support itself, directing production towards specific products by adding MOF on photoactive support.”

1. Introduction

With current environmental changes due to climate change, CO₂ conversion processes have become a major priority. While gas storage is a possible approach [1], the consideration of using CO₂ as feedstock represents an example of closed loop economy to fuel industrial demand. Catalytic approaches often convert CO₂ into carbon monoxide, methanol or methane by hydrogenation, which can then either be used as fuel or precursor for chemicals such as dimethyl ether or C₂+ alcohols [2]. While traditional catalytic approaches often rely on heat and hydrogen, photocatalysis offers a greener approach, using CO₂ and water at much lower temperatures [3].

Carbon nitride (C₃N₄) outstands as photoactive material with several unique properties. The band gap and energy levels enable key reactions such as CO₂ reduction, and its metal-free nature makes it affordable in potential industrial applications, especially compared to TiO₂. The

polymeric nature of C₃N₄ allows for a high degree of tunability either in its morphology [4,5] or through structural modifications [6,7]. The graphitic carbon nitride (gCN) phase is investigated as a metal-free photocatalyst for CO₂ photo-reduction into gas- and liquid-products [8–10]. Doping with Pt and Rh leads to promising catalytic yields [11]. Unlike the transition metals commonly applied to TiO₂, doping onto C₃N₄ uses alkaline metals to enforce charge- and surface-changes [12, 13]. This allows for high tunability, but also brings unique challenges. A major one is faced during catalysis, as the low surface area in gCN leads to low substrate uptake, especially when operating under gas-phase [14]. As an alternative, mesoporous carbon nitrides (mpgCN) can be prepared from a silica template to increase surface area more than tenfold [15,16]. Since binding of active sites can heavily depend on ordered structures and thus on crystallinity, C₃N₄ materials suffer significant drawbacks. Due to the polymeric nature of the C₃N₄ structure and the tendency to direct into melem- and melon-phases beyond the 2D

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structure can lead to poor reproducibility. This is critical when assessing their photocatalytic performance.

Metal-organic frameworks (MOF) can be introduced as mediators of such issues. They show extensive applications in CO₂ storage and potentially in photocatalysis [17]. With a specificity for certain hosts in their cavities, MOFs can act as filter to direct the reaction towards the desired product. The large surface areas and crystalline nature in MOFs can effectively boost substrate binding. MOFs outstand in solid-catalysis as an alternative to achieve similar performance as their homogenous analogues [18,19]. The presence of transition metals and highly customizable organic linkers present an attractive prospect for catalysis, as it combines support and active sites in ordered repetitions. MOFs, however, show low stability under thermal treatment or in the presence of certain solvents. But this is not the case for photocatalysis, where the thermal contribution is usually minimized and compensated by the energy source from light. Most photocatalytic applications are performed under near-ambient temperatures, and gas-phase conditions can reduce the risk of decomposition, turning MOFs into promising candidates for CO₂ photo-conversion reactions.

MOFs have shown photocatalytic consequences when supported. Among them, Cu-based MOFs showed photocatalytic CO₂ reduction activity towards methanol on TiO₂ [20]. The same MOF, however, produced much lower amounts of products onto C₃N₄ [21]. This could be related to the unique interactions of such MOFs with a different photoactive support. Surface and pore structures of these coordination polymers highly depend on synthesis temperature, pressure, pH or the presence of co-ligands, and could affect photocatalytic activity to a large degree. Such morphological changes could either influence the formation of active sites or the MOF-support interface [22,23]. The pore sizes and crystallinity of the support strongly affect MOF formation when synthesized in one-pot reactions [24]. TiO₂, however, facilitates this contact through its O-groups, offering a different context [25]. The more stable interface area, the organic structure and aromatic nature of C₃N₄, however, is likely to cause a different interaction [26]. Studies report MOF growth and then deposition of the photoactive component in a second step, or mixing already-synthesized composites [27]. While this is a relatively easy approach, it offers several possibilities for improvements. Support-MOF interactions will only occur over a shallow interface area. The bulk material will thus contain MOF crystals in the micrometer range, even when any photoactivity will require an electron transfer from the photoactive support, - the most abundant phase - from millimetric particle sizes. A natural MOF growth could lead to a much stronger interaction, nurturing electron flow into more diverse applications, such as thin-films [28]. Thus proper MOF nucleation dynamics can be determinant [29,30]. Any growth will be thermodynamically favored on a support, while metal-ligand interactions with the support can change the MOF topology. Crystal growth will be affected by the support and its ability to facilitate surface interactions. As such, MOF@support heterojunctions are expected to affect the photocatalytic performance dependent on these interactions. In this regard, Cu-based HKUST-1 is an interesting MOF, as it features high tolerance of defects and crystallization environments. It has been investigated as a photocatalyst both with TiO₂ or C₃N₄ [31]. MOF defects would provide abundant binding sites for photocatalysis. The presence of Cu(I) and Cu (II) in HKUST-1 is interesting by advocating donor-acceptor bonding through a charge transfer system [32,33]. HKUST-1 is known to form S-scheme heterojunctions with carbon nitride, effectively forming a stronger interface by initiating a Red-Ox reaction [34]. A comparison to TiO₂ will serve as a means to study the effectiveness and consequences of developing such systems on an aromatic, polymeric support. This allows the use of HKUST-1 as a research subject for deposition on different types of support without explicit adherence to environmental factors. A deeper insight into HKUST-1 deposition on C₃N₄ phases, as compared to TiO₂, will allow to identify unique properties and effects inherent to carbon nitride support. This will lead to a better design of MOF-C₃N₄ heterojunctions in the future, especially related to their photocatalytic

impact.

In this work, we aim to study the effect of the supported MOF morphology on photocatalytic CO₂-reduction reactions. Our goal is to investigate the binding of HKUST-1 on gCN and mpgCN with respect to anatase-TiO₂. We discuss the impact of the support and surface structure on HKUST-1 growth and the consequences in photocatalytic CO₂ reduction in the presence of light and water. The flexible nature of HKUST-1 allows growing MOF structures onto successive layers, with the potential to study the effect of changes in MOF content on distinct supports on photocatalysis. We investigate the optimal formation of the HKUST-1@support composite in terms of photocatalytic performance. This is achieved by testing the different HKUST-1@support composites in a batch reactor under light irradiation. The reactor was used with CO₂ saturated water and the liquid- and gas- phases sampled in set intervals to investigate the reaction evolution with time. We track the deposition of metal and ligand precursors on the support as a function of MOF content. Diffractometric and morphological evidence indicate that HKUST-1 growth on C₃N₄ can be limited to the initial layers, while offering a more and more uniform environment for MOF growth with additional layers. While TiO₂ and C₃N₄ feature drastically different surface topologies, a large surface area in mesoporous C₃N₄ allows for a larger interface area that could affect deposition. Supports favor acetaldehyde production, whilst HKUST-1 narrowed the primary product to ethanol. The HKUST-1 crystallinity is a determinant photocatalytic driver and improves with growing layers. A more crystalline environment on C₃N₄ can be achieved by matching MOF amount for complete surface coverage. This, however, does not occur in TiO₂ composites, which led to much lower MOF contents. As such, this work provides new insights into the behavior of C₃N₄ and TiO₂ as a support for MOF growth. C₃N₄ outstands as more suitable for large scale MOF depositions. This approach can potentially be expanded towards other MOFs deposited onto C₃N₄ to better exploit a photoactive surface in catalysis. This work is expected to clarify concepts related to MOF deposition on such supports but also aims to represent a relevant example to apply photocatalytic reactors as promising tools for CO₂ conversion.

2. Experimental details

2.1. Materials and support preparation

Titanium dioxide (99 %), copper(II)-nitrate hemipentahydrate (98 %), cyanamide (99 % reagent grade), LUDOX HS40 colloid silica solution, melamine (99 %, reagent grade), ethanol, acetone was purchased from Aldrich. Trimesic acid (BTC, 98 %, reagent grade) and ammonium hydrogen difluoride (97 %) were purchased from thermofischer scientific. All reagents were used without further purification. Unless mentioned otherwise, air atmosphere was used during the preparation.

Bulk graphitic carbon nitride (gCN) is prepared via literature procedure. In a standard preparation 50 g of melamine is added to a lid-covered ceramic crucible and heated at 550 °C for 4 h (ramp: 5 °C/min). The bright yellow powder is washed with water (2 × 500 mL), filtered and then dried *in vacuo* at 50 °C for 24 h.

Mesoporous carbon nitride (mpgCN) is prepared via hard-templating using a LUDOX silica template. In a standard preparation, cyanamide (30 g) is mixed with LUDOX HS40 solution (75 g). The solvent is removed *in vacuo* and the viscous residue is then heated at 80 °C under a water bath. After the strongly exothermic reaction, the resulting white powder is gathered, transferred into a lid-covered crucible and heated under nitrogen atmosphere at 550 °C for 4 h (ramp: 2.1 °C/min). The dark yellow powder is gathered and submersed in water (500 mL) in a plastic beaker. Ammonium hydrogen difluoride (120 g) is added to etch the silica template and the solution is stirred 24 h. The solid is then filtered and thoroughly washed by submersion in water (3x300 mL) to remove the remaining HF and SiF₄ phases. The product is filtered and then dried *in vacuo* at 50 °C for 24 h.

2.2. Preparation of HKUST-1 deposition on C₃N₄ or TiO₂ support

To a mixture of C₃N₄ or TiO₂ (4 g) in water is added an excess of Cu(NO₃)₂ hemipentahydrate (2 g) and the mixture is stirred for 12 h to distribute the metal on support. Afterwards, the mixture is filtered without washing. A solution of trimesic acid (1.32 g, corresponding to 10 wt% Cu content in the composite) in ethanol (30 mL) is prepared and the filtered Cu-support is added into it. After stirring for 1 h, the mixture is transferred into an autoclave and heated to 150 °C for 18 h. 10HK@support is then isolated by filtration, washed thoroughly with water (2 × 50 mL) and suspended in methanol (100 mL) to remove leftover Cu and ethanol, then dried *in vacuo* at 50 °C for 24 h. The procedure is repeated one more time, before the product is then further dried under high vacuum at 120 °C for 24 h before photocatalytic use.

The higher (20 wt% / 40 wt%) preparations are then prepared by using the previous HK@support closest in HKUST amount (either 10 wt% or 20 wt%) as a base to prepare the next higher percentage by adding one layer on top of the next, using a solvothermal literature approach to grow the corresponding amount of MOF on the previous layer. In a typical preparation, the support (2 g) and Cu(NO₃)₂ × 2.5 H₂O (732 mg / 2.19 g) are stirred in H₂O (15 mL / 30 mL) and BTC (334 mg / 1.0 g) in ethanol (15 mL / 30 mL) is added. The mixture is stirred for 1 h and then transferred to an autoclave and stored at 150 °C for 18 h. The autoclave is allowed to cool for 6 h and the solid is isolated by filtration, washed thoroughly with water (2x50 mL) and suspended in methanol (100 mL) to remove leftover Cu and ethanol, then dried *in vacuo* at 50 °C for 24 h. The procedure is repeated one more time, before the product is then further dried under high vacuum at 120 °C for 24 h before photocatalytic use.

2.3. Characterization methods

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) measurements of the powdered catalyst were performed using an automatic diffractometer PHILIPS X'PERT PRO operando with Cu-K α radiation and a solid state PIXcel detector. The thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was performed under N₂ and H₂ to learn about the thermal stability of each sample under different atmospheres. These tests were made with TG 209 F3 Tarsus de Netzsch Thermobalance VersaProbe III. The mass-spectrometric measurement was performed on a Pfeiffer Quadstar QMS 422 Mass spectrometer coupled to the TGA system. The samples were introduced into the TGA balance under nitrogen atmosphere, then the gas flow was switched to the measurement's mixture (either 5 % H₂ in Argon, or N₂). After heating, exhaust gases are purged into the MS system. Physical Electronics with a monochromatic Al K α radiation source (E = 1486.7 eV), pre-calibrated with Ag (Ag 3d_{5/2}, 368.26 eV), was used for X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements. TPD-CO₂ experiments were performed on an Autochem II 2920 system from Micromeritics. CO₂-ad- and desorption is measured over a temperature range of 40 °C to 300 °C. Water is first removed by drying the sample in He gas at 120 °C for 1 h, then CO₂ flow is injected at 40 °C and the temperature is raised at 10 °C / min while CO₂ desorption from the sample is measured. Scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM) images, combined with EDS, were done by FEI Talos F200X. UV-Vis response has been measured with UV-Vis-NIR Lambda 950 from Perkin Elmer, moreover, charge recombination has been studied from photoluminescence (PL) for these experiments, a Mai Tai HP laser light source from Spectra-Physics was used. The wavelength of the laser is reduced using an Inspire Blue second harmonic generator (Radiantis) to excite wavelengths from 345 nm to 520 nm. BET surface area was measured using a Quantachrome Autosorb II system using Nitrogen. EPR measurements were taken on a Bruker ELEXSYS 500 spectrometer (X band) at room temperature. The spectrometer was equipped with a super high-Q resonator ER-4123-SHQ and calibrated by a S4 nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) probe. The frequency (~9.395 GHz) was determined with an integrated microwave frequency.

2.4. Photocatalytic measurements

All composites are tested for their photocatalytic activity against the reduction of CO₂ in liquid. A mixture of 30 mL H₂O and 3 mL of TEOA is saturated with CO₂ by bubbling pure CO₂ gas through the liquid for 20 min. The catalyst (600 mg - 1 g) is stirred in this CO₂-saturated H₂O in a closed system. To ensure comparable conditions for both C₃N₄- and TiO₂ support, all catalysts are tested under irradiation with two wavelengths of 370 nm and 427 nm light (irradiance: 200 W/cm²). During the first hour, measurements are taken every 5 min, by sampling 0.5 mL of liquid. Afterwards, during the first 6 h, every hour, 0.5 mL of liquid is sampled, and gas evolution is checked via a connected gas bag. Overnight measurements are taken after 24 h. The liquid samples are analyzed in a GC-MS system (Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010SE with a RTX type wax column), gas products are injected into a GC system (Agilent 7890 A with MS5A type column) to check for reaction products and the catalyst is investigated after use by PXRD and XPS measurements. To verify the impact of photoreduction, the support without HKUST-1 deposition is tested under the same conditions, as is a batch of photocatalyst with CO₂ without light excitation, as well as a batch of photocatalyst under light excitation without CO₂.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural and electrochemical characterization during MOF deposition

PXRD data show differences in C₃N₄-based materials as a function of deposited layer content. Fig. 1 shows a significant shift from reported HKUST-1 signals in favor of a mix of pristine HKUST-1 and unknown phases over the three different deposition cycles. High angle signals of MOF-species are not present or severely reduced and broadened in all cases, as is the case with two main signals at 6.9° and 9.3° at low deposition amounts in gCN and all mpgCN samples. The correlation to pristine HKUST-1 on C₃N₄ is improved over several deposition rounds (as for 40HK@gCN in Fig. 1a). The spectra do not differ as a function of mesoporosity, with the highest MOF-depositions exhibiting the closest similarities to pristine HKUST-1. Moreover, 40HK@mpgCN shows a slight shift in signals, splitting the main C₃N₄ signal at 27.1° (Fig. 1b). TiO₂-based catalysts show the PXRD patterns expected for HKUST-1 during the early layering process (Fig. 1c). MOF signals are visible in all depositions except for 10HK@TiO₂. The 40HK@TiO₂ sample, however, shows signs of reductive processes in the Cu centers and a decomposition of HKUST-1 structure. These are likely to include Cu₂O at 29.5° (110), 36.5° (111), 42.4° (200) and 61.4° (220). In 20- and 40HK@TiO₂ samples, the presence of Cu⁰ at 43.4° (111), 50.5° (200) and 74.1° (220) is likely. The determination however cannot be conclusive due to low intensities at high angles and overlap of Bragg edges with significant TiO₂ signals (Fig. 1c). Interestingly, although reduced species are visible, there is no overlap with the PXRD reported for reduced HKUST-1 at all.

PXRD spectra conclude that HKUST-1 deposition onto TiO₂ leads to an initially better MOF formation, with additional signals (and degradation) visible with increasing deposition cycles. Signals are not completely resolved on TiO₂, and HKUST-1 related signals are very small in all cases, indicating low deposition amount. HK@TiO₂ samples show the opposite behavior as C₃N₄-based samples during the addition of layers. A worse fitting to pristine HKUST-1 over several layering cycles is visible, exactly opposite of what can be observed in C₃N₄. This could be interpreted as a gradual worsening of the MOF composition on TiO₂ support due to reaction conditions as layers are added, likely due to TiO₂ influencing the deposition. In C₃N₄-based materials, layering over 20–40 wt% causes relevant PXRD signals to become more prominent. 40HK@gCN resembles the pattern of the pristine MOF. This transformation appears to take place over two intermediate phases that can be observed in 10HK@gCN and 20HK@gCN. In both gCN and mpgCN-

Fig. 1. PXRD comparison of HK@support composites with pristine HKUST-1 and its reduced derivates. a) PXRD for HK@gCN species. b) PXRD for HK@mpgCN. c) PXRD for HK@TiO₂.

based composites, crystallinity is low and amorphicity only recedes in 40HK@gCN, while mpgCN still retains a large degree in higher deposition amounts. MOF morphology is improved as the number layers and their distance to C₃N₄ is increased. A larger surface area in mpgCN likely requires more MOF to reach the same effect as in gCN. Consequently, signals in 40HK@mpgCN do not show a good correlation, which suggests the malformed MOF is caused by surface interactions with C₃N₄. This is also the consequence of the observed shift in PXRD signals for 20- and 40HK@mpgCN at 27.4°, which shows signs of surface interaction

with the MOF. It should be mentioned that, while reduction of HKUST-1 is reported in literature [35] and the MOF is known to exhibit S-scheme heterojunctions with C₃N₄ that would result in Cu reduction, the data in Fig. 1 do not fit with reported systems. This suggests that interactions with C₃N₄ support as a Red-Ox active coordinative entity initially directs the MOF in the first layer into an unknown topology with a high degree of amorphicity. The PXRD signals over the course of the layering process can be interpreted as a removal of MOF defects by adding additional layers. This suggests, however, an “insulation effect” from previously

Fig. 2. a) HKUST-1 crystals on gCN support in 40HK@gCN, b) HKUST-1 crystals fused to C₃N₄ support and c) 20HK@TiO₂ support. Crystals are loosely attached to TiO₂, while fused to C₃N₄ material. d) Magnification of crystal formations of 40HK@gCN support, e) crystal growth on 40HK@mpgCN support and f) 40 HK@TiO₂ support. Compared to TiO₂-grown MOF, crystals on C₃N₄ possess a diminished habitus with barely noticeable morphology compared to the surrounding support.

deposited layers, preventing a direct MOF reduction through C₃N₄ support with increasing distance. This behavior is unique to C₃N₄-based materials and not exhibited in TiO₂, so a direct relationship to the support photoactivity is unlikely. The differences identified by PXRD are here also assessed by additional surface analyses.

Surface analysis and determination of metal content via SEM-EDX and XRF are expected to provide insights into the growth of MOF crystals on different support surfaces. Fig. 2 shows SEM images of HKUST-1 growth on gCN (Fig. 2a, d), mpgCN with a focus on the interface area (Fig. 2b) and overall morphology in 40HK@mpgCN (Fig. 2e). HKUST-1 crystals are shown on TiO₂ with clear borders to the support (Fig. 2c, f). Crystal growth is visible at low MOF contents, showing crystals of 2–3 μm length for 40HK@gCN. The mpg-CN sample, however, does not form larger crystal formations but exhibits a highly amorphous surface coverage. Large crystals form onto the TiO₂, but these seem only superficially bound to the support. Both C₃N₄-based supports show no clear transition between the crystal and support. A fluent transition between C₃N₄ and MOF can be observed in interface areas that fuses the crystal into the C₃N₄. TiO₂ samples, however, show a much looser adhesion with particles attached to crystal surface that might affect electron transport. This is confirmed in Fig. 3, which shows 5–6 μm diameter HKUST-1 crystals on TiO₂ with a more defined habitus to C₃N₄. In fact, mpgCN-based samples show no defined crystal habitus, with the MOF only being identified by Cu-content using SEM-EDS (Fig. 3b and Fig. 2). The traditional octahedral morphology of HKUST-1, however, is not observed in any of the MOF samples. Indeed, HKUST-1@mpgCN samples often more resemble milled samples [36]. Similar morphologies to HK@gCN and HK@TiO₂ have been reported during the *in-situ* growth onto graphene nanosheets [37,38]. This could be the consequence of saturating the support surface in metal salts before MOF ligand addition. This effect can even be enhanced through the formation of a RedOx-based S-scheme junction, leading to an imbalanced reactant content in the initial layer. The influence of the support on HKUST-1 deposition is even more visible when comparing mpgCN and TiO₂, as mpgCN features a Cu-content with the intended MOF content at high amorphicity. This could be a consequence of templating crystal growth by influencing lattice repetitions (see S1.1, S1.2). In TiO₂, Cu content in low depositions shows high crystallinity, but in very localized depositions, resulting in low amounts. As such, the PXRD data and layering effects during consecutive depositions onto C₃N₄ and TiO₂ supports can be confirmed on a microscopic layer.

Fig. 4 shows several stages of HKUST-1 deposition on mpgCN. The figure shows in descending order the area under SEM magnification as well as the Cu content. A gradual coverage of mpg-C₃N₄ with HKUST-1 is observed as a function of Cu-content via SEM-EDS from a localized coverage (10 wt%) to almost complete coverage (20 wt%). Higher MOF contents are expected to provide complete surface coverage, with SEM-EDS detecting nearly 34 wt% and 38 wt% Cu for 20- and 40HK@mpgCN, respectively. This exceeds the maximum Cu amount

present in pristine HKUST-1 (nearly 29 wt%). Cu-contents, however, are expected to deviate strongly due to the mixed MOF valence state that requires higher Cu-contents to reach charge-balance and could result in CuO micro clusters in the material due to its amorphous nature. The values, however, serve to prove that EDS no longer detects the support underneath. In gCN, this is reached for 40HK@gCN with 33 wt% Cu, while 40HK@TiO₂ only shows nearly 17 wt% Cu. Thus, such EDS methods may serve to determine the surface state that might influence photocatalytic activity, but the low penetration depth limits the detection of the whole metal content, requiring deeper penetration methods.

X-ray fluorescence (XRF) is expected to provide a better overall determination of total Cu content in the composite due to the penetration (up to mm scale) compared to EDS (μm scale). Pristine values as for different Cu contents would follow: 2.9 wt% for 10HK, 5.8 wt% for 20HK, and 11.6 wt% for 40HK. Table 1 compares the Cu content from EDS and XRF measurements. Both gCN- and TiO₂ composites lag behind the mesoporous support (Table 1). This becomes especially obvious at high deposition contents, in which the lower-surface area supports seem to be limited. C₃N₄-based samples hold a much higher content and better dispersed HKUST-1 than TiO₂. Given the different surface coverage and more localized appearance, the calculation of Cu-content on TiO₂ might have a larger margin of error than on C₃N₄. Surface coverage is more easily achieved in mpgCN, whilst gCN-based samples only reach a comparable coverage from SEM-EDX after three HKUST-1 layers. When normalized to available surface area, such effect can be attributed to the porous nature of mpgCN. This is supported by the well-dispersed Cu onto mpgCN-samples. C₃N₄ support seems to act as a rivaling binding partner for Cu-centers, which heavily impacts crystal growth. This tendency might however be influenced by several other factors besides surface effects, such as RedOx-mediated MOF binding onto C₃N₄.

The N₂-adsorption measurements allow detecting structural changes after MOF depositions. Such effect on surface area is evident for mpgCN, especially on the initial layering stages. Surface area drops from 165 m²/g in pristine mpgCN to 75 m²/g in 10HK@mpgCN. The surface area is again increased up to 151 m²/g for 40HK@mpgCN. Even when normalized for the MOF content in the composite, the high surface area featured by pristine HKUST-1 (1600 m²/g) is not translated when the support and MOF are combined. Fig. 5 depicts the pore size distribution of the composite as a function of layers of HKUST-1 on mpgCN. The original mesoporous support with 5 nm pore size shrinks to 4 nm in the first layer of 10HK@mpgCN. An initial drop in surface area can be interpreted as a decreasing amount of mesopores in the composite due to poorly developed HKUST-1 growth on and within the cavities, thereby decreasing their accessibility. This correlates to a long impregnation period of the support with Cu(NO₃)₂ in the initial deposition, which likely contributes to MOF deposition in the mesopores and not just on 10HK@mpgCN extrapore. The increase in surface area with higher MOF loading reflects the microporous HKUST-1 deposition. The results of pore size distribution, however, are unexpected. While it can be assumed

Fig. 3. SEM-EDS measurement of HKUST-1 depositions. a) elemental composition around the HKUST-1 crystal on TiO₂ support, showing a highly localized dispersion of Cu within the MOF structure. b) Distribution of Cu (purple) in 40HK@mpgCN.

Fig. 4. SEM-EDX measurements of HKUST-1 on mpg-CN at: a) 10 wt% MOF on mpgCN support on carbon tape, with EDS of copper content (d) and a magnification of Cu deposited area, showing N and Cu content (g). b) SEM of 20 wt% HKUST-1 on mpgCN support on carbon tape, showing the Cu content (e), as well as a magnification of the Cu deposited area (h). c) SEM of 40 wt% MOF on mpgCN support on carbon tape, with Cu content of the particles (f), as well as a magnification of one of the areas (i).

Table 1

Cu-content measured via XRF and EDS for HKUST-1 deposited on gCN, mpgCN and TiO₂ correlated to the nominal content deposited during preparation.

Sample	gCN (wt% Cu)		mpgCN (wt% Cu)		TiO ₂ (wt% Cu)	
	XRF	EDS	XRF	EDS	XRF	EDS
10HK	1.3	0.6	3.2	5.8	0.6	5.9
20HK	3.5	15.0	5.7	33.4	1.3	13.7
40HK	6.1	33.0	9.3	38.0	5.8	16.6

Fig. 5. Pore size distribution of HK@mpgCN-composites calculated by DFT (carbon, slit pore) for different deposition layers of HKUST-1.

that the first HKUST-1 deposition partially blocked access to mpgCN pores by forming an inside layer, additional layering of the MOF creates entirely new pore structures that exhibit distinct pore sizes up to the original pore size diameter of mpgCN. Pores lead to a much wider range of diameters with increasing deposition amount. This could infer a minimum pore size for HKUST-1 penetration to enable MOF growth on deeper layers.

Thermogravimetric analyses show that the decomposition of all HKUST-1 derivatives begins at 300 °C, followed by the support at 400 °C for mpgCN or at 500 °C for gCN. The mpgCN case shows a much more gradual weight loss. TiO₂-based samples are not expected to show decomposition (see S2.2–7). Isotherm methods at 150 °C, 175 °C and 200 °C show stable behavior in gCN and TiO₂-samples, with a gradual decomposition already setting in at 225 °C. Mesoporous mpgCN samples are more distinct and already show a slow mass loss before MOF decomposition over the entire range, which is not present for gCN or TiO₂. *In operando* XAS shows an increasing reduction of Cu(II) centers on C₃N₄ starting at 220 °C, showcasing a possible source for the observed instability in the Red-Ox heterojunction (see S2.8). Other than a change in oxidation state, the observed weight loss could be attributed to the release of water trapped in the mesoporous material. Thus, the behavior at 200 °C was investigated in detail. TGA-MS experiments for HK@mpgCN provide a more detailed assessment (see S2.1). The 2D-spectrum measured by the MS at a temperature range of 50–300 °C identifies the gases liberated during this period. Organic solvents from synthesis are not observed (see S2.1, 2.3). The TGA-MS analysis shows a slow release of gaseous products from 40HK@mpgCN with a peak at 220 °C. When analyzed by MS, this can be interpreted as a structural collapse into O₂, CO₂ and CH₄, possibly indicating an ongoing photo-reductive process in the pore-space. This is likely added by water and CO₂ from air confined in blocked pores to produce O₂ and CH₄ during a

photocatalytic reaction. The TGA-MS confirms the results observed in SEM and pore size analysis for mpgCN concerning pore blockage.

Temperature programmed desorption (TPD) experiments were performed on graphitic and mesoporous carbon nitride samples. The results confirm differences in CO₂-binding in C₃N₄ dependent on morphology (see Fig. 6). While pristine mpgCN has higher binding capabilities than gCN, their respective heterojunctions exhibit the opposite behavior in CO₂ adsorption. HKUST-1 deposition shows a negative effect on CO₂-binding. While these differences are small in gCN (Fig. 6a), HK@mpgCN samples bind much less CO₂ than on gCN nitride with a severely lower adsorbed CO₂ value at 160 °C ($3.46 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ in 40HK@gCN, Fig. 6a, against $7.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ in 40HK@mpgCN, Fig. 6b), which makes up the main signal in the pristine samples. Instead, desorption at lower temperatures is increased, but still under the values observed in the pristine supports. Among samples containing similar HKUST contents, the 40HK@gCN sample shows five times higher adsorbed CO₂ desorption than 20HK@mpgCN (Fig. 6). If normalized to surface area, an impact of more than 50 times on CO₂ adsorption for gCN is observed. This serves to show the effect of HKUST-1 morphology on carbon nitride, and could be an indication of pore blockage onset, which might translate into differences in photocatalytic activity in liquid phase.

Fig. 7 shows UV-Vis absorbance data from HK@gCN and HK@mpgCN in different deposition amounts, as well as the difference with respect to pure HKUST-1. The UV-Vis data show a shift in absorption from the maxima reported for HKUST-1 at 710 nm to 382 nm (Fig. 7c), indicative of a Red-Ox process as in a S-scheme heterojunction [34]. Changes during layering HKUST-1 both on gCN or mpgCN are also observed (Fig. 7a). A Red-Ox interaction is not reported in literature for TiO₂ composites, which exhibit the absorption bands from HKUST-1 and support at 710 nm and 354 nm (Fig. 7b), respectively. Low intensities in HKUST-1 absorbance maxima in TiO₂ composites are observed when compared to the absence of MOF. This can be interpreted as a sign of low deposition amount. In both gCN and mpgCN, an increase in VIS absorption is detected with deposited HKUST-1 content. This effect is more pronounced in mpgCN support, likely due to much larger amounts of deposited MOF (Fig. 7a). Absorption maxima characteristic of supports, however, are still preserved, indicative that the light absorption capacity of the photoactive components is largely unaffected. This allows to fully exploit the high surface area offered by the material, which is especially relevant for testing under photocatalytic conditions.

The PXRD and SEM methods in the present section reveal significant differences between the different support types, which can affect surface binding and charge transport through the composite. The deposition method seems promising for C₃N₄-based systems. The metal content or the UV-Vis assessment, however, confirm the absence of adequate

HKUST-1 layering onto TiO₂. Mesoporous C₃N₄ seems to outstand from its graphitic analogue, as it contains higher HKUST-1 contents, but with a significant influence of the support on HKUST-1 structure. Such differences are thus expected to provide distinct photocatalytic activity, especially when productivities in catalysis highly depend on CO₂ substrate binding and light penetration, as discussed later.

3.2. Photocatalytic measurements

The photocatalytic data will be assessed using the real metal content as in Table 1. Although it is debatable whether SEM-EDS might give a more detailed analysis of surface states during photocatalysis, we will use XRF values to avoid misinterpretations from substrate- and light-penetration during catalysis. The initial pH of the solution during photocatalysis is set at 9, which changes to pH 8 over 24 h. The basicity of the solution is largely attributed to TEOA. Readings indicate that while CO₂ levels in solution are decreasing noticeably over 24 h, they are still being detected in solution after photocatalytic tests. With the CO₂ species in water being pH-dependent, this might however affect the reaction.

Fig. 8 compares the photoactivity for acetaldehyde and ethanol production as a function of metal content and type of support after 2 h of reaction. Pristine C₃N₄ and TiO₂ supports show an acetaldehyde production of over 1 μmol/g_{cat}h in the initial stage of the photocatalytic reaction. TiO₂-based samples show the best photocatalytic performance. gCN and mpgCN supports, in the absence of HKUST-1, perform almost equally well, which is unexpected considering the effect of surface area in photocatalysis. The presence of deposited HKUST-1 shifts production towards ethanol, while acetaldehyde productivity is still be detected. This is evident for all cases except for 10HK@gCN. In the case of gCN samples, ethanol productivity increases with increasing MOF coverage. The mpgCN- and TiO₂-based samples, however, do not follow this pattern, as mpgCN-based samples do not show noticeable differences in acetaldehyde- and ethanol production for different MOF contents, whereas TiO₂-based samples show a decrease in productivity.

The effect of C₃N₄ on photocatalysis is likely related to structural differences (as observed in PXRD), with the higher surface contact in mpgCN reducing photocatalytic activity. This is caused by an improper growth of HKUST-1 on mpgCN compared to gCN (as discussed in Section 3.1). This can also be observed in TiO₂ samples, as the higher HKUST-1 crystallinity in the first depositions leads to an increase in ethanol productivity. With increasing layers, the decomposition of the TiO₂ reduces photocatalytic activity. All C₃N₄ or TiO₂ composites exhibit lower acetaldehyde productivity than in the pristine support (Fig. 8), but their long-term stability also differs. This is shown in Table 2, which normalizes productivity by Cu content as a means to determine MOF

Fig. 6. CO₂ temperature programmed desorption (TPD) for: a) 40HK@gCN against gCN; b) 40HK@mpgCN against mpgCN.

Fig. 7. UV-Vis spectra for HK@CN (a) and HK@TiO₂ (b) with increasing amounts of HKUST deposited on the support. While an increasing absorption can be observed in the C₃N₄ materials, TiO₂ is impacted only slightly in the highest deposition amounts. c) RedOx-induced shift in absorbance between pristine HKUST-1 and HK@CN composites.

Fig. 8. Ethanol and acetaldehyde productivity from CO₂ and water for HK@ C₃N₄ and HK@TiO₂ materials after 2 h reaction.

Table 2

Performance of C₃N₄- and TiO₂-based composites in photocatalytic CO₂-reduction as a function of Cu content after 1 h and 24 h of light irradiation.

Samples	Turnover rate (μmol _{prod} μmol _{Cu} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) after 1 h		Turnover rate (μmol _{prod} μmol _{Cu} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) after 24 h	
	Acetaldehyde	Ethanol	Acetaldehyde	Ethanol
10HK@TiO ₂	23901	undetectable	815	148
20HK@TiO ₂	1721	218	57	19
40HK@TiO ₂	928	203	44	5
10HK@ gCN	7	22	374	7
20HK@ gCN	808	1376	64	75
40HK@ gCN	798	3295	59	162
10HK@ mpgCN	633	255	12	undetectable
20HK@ mpgCN	2058	247	17,334	302
40HK@ mpgCN	306	1	17	undetectable

deposition on the photocatalytic support. When investigating long-term behavior, a lower but more consistent activity can be observed for C₃N₄-based composites. In all cases however, photocatalysts degrade over time. This drop in activity cannot be attributed to the absence of CO₂ in the reaction solution (conversion is below 1 % for pristine support and

the heterojunctions). The largest decrease in activity after 24 h can be observed in bulk TiO₂. This deactivation does not recover initially observed acetaldehyde productivity as seen in pristine support, so both the MOF and the support in the heterojunction are affected. C₃N₄-based samples exhibit better long-term stability. When the photocatalytic activity is normalized by Cu measured by XRF, the 40HK@gCN exhibits the best ethanol productivity. Lower MOF contents (20HK@gCN) yield lower productivities with predominantly acetaldehyde production. Higher Cu-contents in gCN lead to higher ethanol production, but turnover rates for acetaldehyde do not accordingly increase with MOF content. This leaves the question whether additional MOF layers lead to adverse photocatalytic effects due to minor amounts of acetaldehyde as intermediate, as discussed later. The mpgCN-based samples again show a particular behavior, with a lower ethanol productivity (20HK@mpgCN) but higher acetaldehyde productivity than gCN after 1 h. The activity drop in 40HK@mpgCN could be attributed to an uneven MOF growth causing lack of photocatalytic control, as expected from smaller layers onto high-surface C₃N₄. This effect, however, is further enhanced with increasing deposition of a MOF featuring poor crystallinity, leading to a faster degradation at high MOF contents while the actual MOF barely contributes to the photocatalytic activity, even when compared to gCN support.

TiO₂-based samples show very good turnover rates, especially to acetaldehyde (Table 2). Ethanol productivity, however, is poor due to low HKUST-1 content. These examples highlight the relevance of

crystallinity in catalysis, as TiO₂-based systems have a more established habitus. Structural degradation, as for 40HK@TiO₂, however, leads to lower productivity. TiO₂ samples show lower ethanol productivity than for C₃N₄, which is here attributed to a more defined physical separation of heterojunction interface. These results suggest that TiO₂ produces more acetaldehyde than C₃N₄ but does not outstand to catalyze into ethanol. The productivities for ethanol fit TiO₂-based reports for CO₂ valorization using HKUST-1, but the intermediates considerably differ [21]. Reported studies produce nearly 43 μmol CO g_{CAT}⁻¹h⁻¹, 1.3 μmol ethanol g_{CAT}⁻¹h⁻¹ and 0.1 μmol methanol g_{CAT}⁻¹h⁻¹ on NH₂-modified HKUST-1. Most studies detect gaseous products such as CO or CH₄, which can also be observed in CO₂ photoreduction in glycerol/water solutions [39]. The present work, however, only detects liquid-phase products. Even if taking into account carbon stoichiometric differences in C₁ to C₂ conversion, acetaldehyde productivity is lower than reported but ethanol productivity is higher. On the other hand, the production of acetaldehyde is well documented in graphitic- and hard-templated mesoporous C₃N₄ [40,41]. This is of particular concern as HKUST-1 can oxidize the alcohol [42]. This presents a challenge, since the produced ethanol can act as sacrificial agent, leading to non-rigorous conclusions. This will be addressed in Section 3.3 by assessing the photocatalytic reaction pathways.

The effect of time on photocatalytic behavior is also here assessed in detail. Fig. 9a shows acetaldehyde and ethanol productivity as a function of reaction time for selected 20 wt% and 40 wt% HKUST-1 samples. The TiO₂-support shows the highest acetaldehyde productivity after 1 h, whilst gCN and mpgCN show lower but more stable productivity. Indeed, the 40HK@gCN sample reaches similar acetaldehyde rates as 20HK@TiO₂. For ethanol, gCN-based samples even surpass highly crystalline HKUST-1@TiO₂ samples, leading to higher alcohol productivity in the earlier stages (Fig. 9b). Mesoporous samples yield the lowest acetaldehyde and ethanol productivity. In all cases, all rates drop sharply within 4 h, which then tends to decline to much lower values. The observed behavior fits characterization measurements, as ethanol productivity in TiO₂ is much lower due to lower HKUST-1 content and faster decomposition. The crystalline 40HK@gCN sample, however, possesses the highest HKUST-1 content and thus is the best performer in terms of total ethanol production. Mesoporous samples most likely suffer due to the improper MOF growth on the support and as a result show a much lower ethanol production. Acetaldehyde production decreases due to the higher surface exposure of mpgCN towards HKUST-1 (and the reaction environment). With an initial loading of 990 μmol CO₂ (as per solubility of CO₂ in pure water of 1.45 g/L), CO₂ conversion reaches 0.74 % and 0.47 % CO₂ in pristine gCN and TiO₂ supports, respectively. While 10HK@TiO₂ shows 0.15 % CO₂-conversion,

40HKUST1@gCN shows 0.37 % conversion with 63 % ethanol selectivity. In mesoporous samples, 10HK@mpgCN reaches 0.29 % CO₂ conversion with 98 % for acetaldehyde selectivity. This suggests that mesoporous samples compete with gCN for acetaldehyde production, but catalysis into ethanol is highly affected by HKUST-1 crystallinity. In TiO₂-based samples, the deposited MOF content seems to be the limiting factor, preventing higher CO₂ conversion.

3.3. Assessment of photocatalytic reaction pathways and role of sacrificial agent

The studies on CO₂ photoreduction into gaseous CH₄/CO or methanol claim that intermediates follow either carbene or formaldehyde pathways [43]. C₂ products are not common and rely on dimerization processes that likely require a stabilization step on the support [44]. In this case, formaldehyde outstands as the major intermediate of the reductive process to form bivalent aldehydes (glyoxals) that can then be reduced and dehydroxylated further. GC-MS allows to identify various side products in minor quantities beyond acetaldehyde and ethanol. HKUST-1 solely does not show CO₂-reduction photoactivity, as measured by GC-MS (see S3.3). Main products can clearly be identified as C₂-molecules (acetaldehyde, ethanol) in all supports, while the support without any HKUST-1 exhibits acetaldehyde productivity and allows for the detection of formaldehyde at advanced stages of the photocatalytic reaction (see S3.4–3.5). Acetaldehyde is the main product at low HKUST-1 depositions, but higher MOF amounts enhance the probability to form ethanol. This suggests that the reductive pathway into ethanol is the rate limiting step in the presence of HKUST-1. This theory can be tested by feeding acetaldehyde to photocatalyst solutions without saturating the solution with CO₂. Under light irradiation and TEOA as a sacrificial agent, HKUST-1@gCN and HKUST-1@mpgCN composites produce ethanol, whilst pristine supports and HKUST-1 on their own do not produce ethanol (S3.6–3.14). Compared to the results of feeding CO₂, it is interesting to see that while mpgCN-based photocatalysts give similar productivity, the productivity in gCN based photocatalyst is lower when using acetaldehyde compared to the use of CO₂. This again can be explained by referring to the available surface area, with mpgCN-based systems being much more accessible to larger molecules. These results imply a dependence of ethanol production on the presence of not only HKUST-1, but the assembled heterojunction (Fig. 10). The proposal for ethanol production being the rate-limiting is also supported by the lack of C₁-products, since a possible dimerization of formaldehyde while still bound to support would allow a fast conversion into C₂-intermediates. Assuming dimerization requires a re-adsorption onto the support or the MOF, kinetics would be slower and

Fig. 9. a) Acetaldehyde productivity for C₃N₄- and TiO₂-based composites and pristine support as a function of reaction time. b) Ethanol productivity for selected C₃N₄- and TiO₂-based composites as a function of reaction time. The remaining samples are presented for comparison in SI (see S3.1, S3.2).

Fig. 10. Reaction pathway proposal for the conversion of CO₂ and water in HK@C₃N₄ and HK@TiO₂ samples under photocatalysis largely adherent to the glyoxal pathway [45], including the participation of its components in the various reaction steps.

thus the presence of C1-intermediates would be much more likely. On the other hand, if the desorption of acetaldehyde and its adsorption onto HKUST-1 is a requirement for ethanol, its productivity would be the rate-limiting step on MOFs.

GC-MS detects intermediates such as formaldehyde, oxalaldehyde and some of their ethane ethers and esters (see S3.3, 3.4). This suggests a hydroxyl-radical pathway through the gradual reduction of oxidized acetaldehyde derivatives over oxaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetaldehyde. The former, however, cannot be isolated in the reaction mixture. Interestingly, no decarbonylation into CO, CH₄ or methanol takes place. In addition, 1,2-ethanediol is detected in several samples. The presence of diol is of particular interest, since it is expected as an end product in the reaction coordinate during photocatalysis or as a result of the reduction of 2-hydroxyacetaldehyde. The first option is an oxidative step in a reductive pathway and thereby a sign of using ethanol as a sacrificial agent (in parallel to TEOA). The second is a reduction of acetaldehyde derivatives in a branching reaction towards a diol side-product, which cannot be conclusively discarded.

In addition, ethanol can lead to confusion as it's used as solvent during MOF preparation and can be trapped within the structure and only released in contact with H₂O or under photocatalysis. Thorough washing and drying, however, excluded the storage of ethanol in both support and HKUST-1 blank samples. Acetaldehyde is also excluded as a byproduct from ethanol oxidation (see S2.3, S3.2). The TEOA sacrificial agent, however, can also degrade to ethanol as product in certain reductive pathways. To exclude such a possibility, we replaced the sacrificial agent with methanol or 2-butanol. Both sacrificial agents show the same photoreduction products as for TEOA, and additional oxidation side products (see S3.4, S3.5). When a large surplus of sacrificial agent is applied (10 mL vs. 0.1 mL), the use of methanol and 2-butanol only showed minimal impact on productivity (see S3.15–3.17). The presence of acetaldehyde can be confirmed in tests featuring carbon nitride and, more importantly, pristine HKUST-1, whilst methanol predominantly formed formaldehyde as the primary oxidation product. As for pristine HKUST-1, this likely indicates a breaking down of butanol or its oxidized species into acetaldehyde. In fact, the presence of propanal is also detected. This suggests an indiscriminate breaking of carbon bonds to produce lower chain products from butanol. In case of methanol, the presence of formaldehyde is expected as the primary oxidation product of the sacrificial product, and could in theory feed into the production of acetaldehyde in a similar manner to the conversion of CO₂. Still, acetaldehyde cannot be observed in the initial hours of the reaction, which could indicate a blockage of active sites by the surplus of methanol as a rivaling (or preferred) substrate. Fig. 11 shows a schematic overview of detected products as a function of type of sacrificial agent. Amongst them, we detect formaldehyde, acetic acid and its methyl-, as well as ethyl-ester for methanol or 2-butanone, 1,2-butanediol, 1-butanol and acetic acid ethyl ester for 2-butanol. This also serves to elucidate eventual complications to assess the origin of ethanol during photocatalysis. Since butanol is oxidized into butanone, it is likely that ethanol could be used in a similar fashion by re-oxidizing products to acetaldehyde. This would eventually lead to the accumulation and breakdown of side products in solution over longer time periods, decreasing product concentration. Such behavior can lead to unexpected changes in productivity over time and could even

Fig. 11. Detected oxidation products of different sacrificial agents during the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ using 10HK@TiO₂, 40HK@gCN and 40HK@mpgCN.

lead to a breakdown into CO or CH₄. The reaction period in the present study, however, does not enable such conversion pathways.

Methanol as a sacrificial agent yields more than twice ethanol productivity than TEOA, but lower acetaldehyde productivity. This is likely caused by inserting formaldehyde intermediates into the reaction chain. This can be seen most prominently in 40HK@mpgCN, which produces 2.2 μmol acetaldehyde g_{cat}⁻¹h⁻¹ and 0.4 μmol ethanol g_{cat}⁻¹h⁻¹ after 1 h with TEOA, but with methanol it only produces 0.3 μmol acetaldehyde g_{cat}⁻¹h⁻¹ and 1.0 μmol ethanol g_{cat}⁻¹h⁻¹. This also serves as indirect proof that the observed activity is not the result of TEOA turning into decomposition products by degrading into 2-ethanolamine and 2-hydroxyacetaldehyde via a reductive pathway, as the productivity from TEOA-decomposition would result in much higher values [46]. As such, acetaldehyde is identified as the major primary product of the photocatalytic pathway, which in large parts depends on the support. In cases where acetaldehyde production depends on a formaldehyde precursor and not on CO₂, activity in mesoporous CN in particular is higher, indicating an easier acceptance as a substrate. The same is true for feeding acetaldehyde to produce ethanol, which has a large impact on ethanol productivity in mesoporous photocatalyst, but a negligible one in ones based on graphitic carbon nitride. In accordance to findings on CO₂-binding on the photocatalysts (see Fig. 6), this strongly suggests a dependence of CO₂-binding steps on the supports, while HKUST-1 catalyzes acetaldehyde conversion into ethanol, as the bare support cannot

catalyze this step. This way, the data in the present work proposes a deviation from the traditional pathway of the glyoxal pathway using HKUST-1.

3.4. Post-catalytic characterization

The photocatalytic differences observed in Section 3.3 are also expected to be seen for C₃N₄ and TiO₂ composites before and after catalysis. A visible change in the composite is observed after irradiation with light in the presence of water and CO₂ for 48 h. C₃N₄-based samples preserve its yellow-brown color but express a blue coloration of the liquid, indicating the presence of Cu²⁺ species. Instead, the TiO₂-based samples show a discoloration, changing from blue into purple composite without visibly leaching into the liquid (see S3.6). This behavior is well reported on TiO₂ and is often associated with an increasing content of Cu⁺ and Cu⁰. This can be interpreted as a Cu⁰ photodeposition on TiO₂, with Cu within HKUST-1 actively reduced and bound to TiO₂ surface, leading to deactivation. In C₃N₄-based systems, this does not happen to the same extent, and instead, the MOF itself disintegrates, leaching excess Cu²⁺ into solution. The blue Cu²⁺ species can easily be identified as Cu²⁺-hydroxide, which indicates a hydroxylation process in water due to the inherent instability of HKUST-1. Indeed, post-catalytic analysis of the composites using PXRD reveals the presence of Cu(0) in TiO₂ samples, but the presence of Cu(I) in the form of Cu₂O in C₃N₄ samples, with additional signals indicating a smaller presence of Cu(0) (See S4.2). While no leaching can be detected in the case of TiO₂, it can be assumed that a complete reduction took place. In the case of the carbon nitride sample, Cu(II) and ligand are present in the liquid after the photocatalytic reaction, while the support binds leftover Cu₂O and traces of Cu(0). This proves a reduction of the photocatalyst in both cases, but to varying degrees.

The underlying mechanisms of such observations after catalysis are here elaborated by XPS and EPR measurements. While XPS analyses provide insights about Cu content and changes in the connectivity and oxidation states of components, EPR allows to investigate the state of the metal environment by measuring the paramagnetic moment of the Cu center. XPS methods show a shrinking Cu²⁺ content for both C₃N₄ and TiO₂ composites (see S3.7-S11). This is expected for HK@C₃N₄ due to Cu²⁺ leaching, but TiO₂ samples show the shift towards lower oxidation numbers without leaching. Besides the metal content, XPS characterizations of the pre- and post-catalysis solid samples show no distinctions between C₃N₄ and TiO₂. The XPS data in Fig. 12 shows N1s shifts to characterize the C₃N₄-surface after photocatalysis beyond Cu-signals. A small shift to higher binding energies from 400.4 eV to 400.8 eV is

Fig. 12. XPS characterization of N1s edges in 40HK@gCN, showing a shift in pre- and postcatalysis samples after 2d of light irradiation.

observed, indicative of a lower electron density on the surface level, which could be a sign of stronger C₃N₄-Cu-interactions. This means that catalytic activity modifies the C₃N₄-surface even under MOF coverage, which could be both taken as a sign of an active heterojunction, as well as a likely shift on a structural level as a consequence of photocatalytic activity.

We also performed EPR measurements on HK@mpgCN samples to clarify the implications regarding HKUST-1 quality on mesoporous C₃N₄. These are shown in Fig. 13 for pre- and post-catalytic samples. A pattern indicative of Cu²⁺ is still present in the used sample, but at lower g-values than in the pre-catalysis samples. This is indicative of a structural change in the MOF system. The presence of three different g-values in the pre-catalysis HK@mpgCN sample is of particular interest, as it suggests the presence of an intermediate state relying on both d_{z²} and d_{x²-y²} orbital ground states in mpgCN (Fig. 12a). This then returns to a more optimal octahedral symmetry featuring d_{x²-y²} ground states after photocatalysis, although at exceptionally high g₁ values (Fig. 12b). In conclusion, both EPR and XPS allow an interpretation of the degradation that follows characterization and previous observations. While an initial MOF leaching from the photocatalyst occurs, it can be assumed that the MOF onto C₃N₄ is bound more strongly and thus is not severely affected by a leaching effect. At the same time, EPR characterization suggests that HKUST-1 containing Cu²⁺ is still present on the C₃N₄ material after catalysis. There are indications that the MOF changes its structure over the course of the experiment, assuming an octahedral environment. Interestingly, while a similar environment should be expected in an ideal HKUST-1 structure, the reported g-values and symmetry of HKUST-1[47] are a better fit for the pre-catalysis sample (g₁=2.340, g₂=2.05 and an additional signal at g₃=2.149). With the third signal attested to antiferromagnetic Cu-Cu interactions, a compression of the structure with widening Cu-Cu distances seems to be the explanation for the drop in photocatalytic activity in C₃N₄ samples. As such, EPR confirms the formation of HKUST-1 on mpgCN-based support and also allows an observation regarding the slow deactivation of the composite on a structural level in the MOF compound, as shown by the photocatalytic data in Section 3.3. This confirms the catalytic potential of such HKUST-1 deposition methods to produce relevant chemicals, but still the MOF stability remains a challenging matter.

4. Conclusions

This work shows that when Cu-based HKUST-1 is deposited onto photoactive supports, C₃N₄ exhibits particular structural differences compared to TiO₂. C₃N₄ allows for high MOF contents but at low quality, whereas TiO₂ allows for highly crystalline, but loosely bound coordination compounds. As such, there is a need to adapt impregnation and deposition methods when working with C₃N₄ materials. A layering deposition method for HKUST-1 leads to much better MOF binding on C₃N₄, and an improvement of the HKUST-1 structure over several layers. This behavior can be observed in bulk samples as well as their mesoporous analogues and affects both MOF content and dispersion. As a result, C₃N₄ can facilitate coordinative HKUST-1 binding to support without additional anchors or modifications. When depositing HKUST-1 on C₃N₄, surface area is determined by the mesoporous support and HKUST-1 contributes marginally, effectively reducing the impact of high-surface area MOFs. While increasing layers on mpgCN initially decreases surface area, the microporosity of HKUST-1, however, enhances surface area and pore size during the deposition of several layers. An effect of light penetration through the initial MOF layer cannot be ruled out and needs to be more thoroughly studied, where UV-Vis absorbance shows no signs of a shift in maxima with several layers deposited. The difference in interaction can also be observed during the photoreduction of CO₂ in water. The composites with highest crystallinity show the best photocatalytic performance, which can be improved by layering the MOF on C₃N₄-based materials. In TiO₂, this does not seem to be the case and layering HKUST-1 has a negative impact on

Fig. 13. EPR measurements for pre- (a) and post-catalysis (b) samples for 40HK@mpgCN measured at 5 K.

crystallinity and photocatalysis. Interestingly, while Red-Ox based S-scheme heterojunctions are known to impact activity in a positive way on photocatalysts like TiO₂, this study observes the opposite in HKUST-1@C₃N₄. The activity of the photocatalyst improves with increasing distance of the MOF to the support (and with it, reducing the impact of the Red-Ox bonding on the interface). Even with both C₃N₄ and TiO₂ supports possessing a vastly different composition, they show selectivity of up to 63 % to ethanol over acetaldehyde. The composite, however, does not possess long-term stability. While turnover rates for gCN-based samples increase for ethanol with HKUST-1 content, they are stable for ethanol in TiO₂. It can be observed that higher HKUST-1 convert faster acetaldehyde into ethanol, reaching peak productivity and accelerating MOF degradation. Experiments on high-surface area mpgCN show that the same deposition amount as in gCN does not reach similar productivity, with turnover rates behaving erratically due to structural issues of MOF deposition. It is therefore likely that the deposition amount has to be scaled in relation to the surface size, with initial MOF-C₃N₄ interactions on the interface leading to a poor MOF morphology. By building on observed differences, we are currently studying the impact of MOF- and non-porous coordination polymers on graphitic and mesoporous C₃N₄. An understanding of the differences in photoactive support and a proper control of deposition on different C₃N₄ phases is expected to bridge the gap in photocatalytic activity to TiO₂-based systems. This way, it is expected that such photocatalysts can become a relevant solution to convert CO₂ with water into relevant chemicals.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

H. Gomez: Resources, Data curation. **S. Vaquero:** Resources, Data curation. **P. Nimax:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **C. Múgica:** Resources, Data curation. **I. Agirrezabal-Telleria:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103098](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103098).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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